

SCI-CONF.COM.UA

**FUNDAMENTAL AND
APPLIED RESEARCH IN
THE MODERN WORLD**

**PROCEEDINGS OF IX INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE
APRIL 14-16, 2021**

**BOSTON
2021**

FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED RESEARCH IN THE MODERN WORLD

Proceedings of IX International Scientific and Practical Conference

Boston, USA

14-16 April 2021

Boston, USA

2021

UDC 001.1

The 9th International scientific and practical conference “Fundamental and applied research in the modern world” (April 14-16, 2021) BoScience Publisher, Boston, USA. 2021. 756 p.

ISBN 978-1-73981-124-2

The recommended citation for this publication is:

Ivanov I. Analysis of the phaunistic composition of Ukraine // Fundamental and applied research in the modern world. Proceedings of the 9th International scientific and practical conference. BoScience Publisher. Boston, USA. 2021. Pp. 21-27. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/ix-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-fundamental-and-applied-research-in-the-modern-world-14-16-aprelya-2021-goda-boston-ssa-arhiv/>.

Editor

Komarytskyy M.L.

Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor

Collection of scientific articles published is the scientific and practical publication, which contains scientific articles of students, graduate students, Candidates and Doctors of Sciences, research workers and practitioners from Europe, Ukraine, Russia and from neighbouring countries and beyond. The articles contain the study, reflecting the processes and changes in the structure of modern science. The collection of scientific articles is for students, postgraduate students, doctoral candidates, teachers, researchers, practitioners and people interested in the trends of modern science development.

e-mail: boston@sci-conf.com.ua

homepage: <https://sci-conf.com.ua>

©2021 Scientific Publishing Center “Sci-conf.com.ua” ®

©2021 BoScience Publisher ®

©2021 Authors of the articles

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	<i>Avdimirets N. V.</i> THE DISCURSIVE DIMENSION OF HAPPINESS AND THE ECONOMY.	13
2.	<i>Aliyeva I. F.</i> ANATOMICAL STUDIES OF FESTUCA OVINA.	18
3.	<i>Agayeva G., Nedashkovskaya T.</i> THE ROLE OF HYPERBOLE IN THE POEMS OF MAGTYMGULY AND THEIR TRANSLATIONS INTO RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH.	22
4.	<i>Agayeva O., Agayev M.</i> HISTORICAL PERSONALITIES IN THE POEMS OF MAGTYMGULY PYRAGY AND THE PROBLEMS OF LITERARY TRANSLATION INTO RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.	32
5.	<i>Bayqabilov K. M., Safarov U. X., Karakulov N. M.</i> DEGREE OF LEARNING, TOPONIMIC CLASSIFICATION AND NATURAL GEOGRAPHICAL ASPECTS OF EUROPEAN COUNTRIES.	41
6.	<i>Belova I. M., Zavytii O. P.</i> DIRECTIONS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF TERRITORIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN UKRAINE.	51
7.	<i>Borisenko T. I., Petrova E. I.</i> MODAL VERBAL CONSTRUCTIONS WITH ‘MUST’ IN THE TEXT CORPORA OF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL DISCOURSE.	62
8.	<i>Eminov A. M., Ruzmetov I., Eminov A. A., Boymurodova M. T., Vacasov C., Abrayev M. S.</i> COMPOSITION AND PROPERTIES OF SILICA FROM RICE HUSK.	67
9.	<i>Karatieieva S. Yu.</i> MODERN STANDARDS OF EDUCATION FOR TRAINING OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED SPECIALISTS.	76
10.	<i>Klimko Yu. E.</i> SYNTHESIS OF ADAMANTYL CONTAINING 3-OXO TETRAHYDROISOQUINOLINE IS USING AMIGO ALKYLATING REAGENTS.	82
11.	<i>Kliunina N.</i> INTEGRATION – TODAY’S NECESSITY.	84
12.	<i>Mammadov S. Je., Hasanova R. Yu., Alixanova A. Z., Allahverdiyev T. G.</i> DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY.	91
13.	<i>Melnyk G., Yarnykh T., Yuryeva G.</i> INVESTIGATION OF THE STABILITY OF AN EXTEMPORANEOUS SUSPENSION OF BISMUTH BASIC NITRATE.	98
14.	<i>Salmanov V. M., Ibragimov B. G.</i> THE INTERBAND LIGHT ABSORPTION OF QUANTUM DOT SUPERLATTICE.	103

15.	<i>Shevchenko V. V., Shayda V. P., Pototsky D.</i> THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL DIRECTIONS FOR THE TURBOGENERATORS CREATION, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE ELECTRIC POWER INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT.	110
16.	<i>Sopel O. M., Sopel O. V., Lototska O. V., Kopach O. Ye., Fedoriv O. Ye., Melnyk N. A., Yurchyshyn O. M., Bilukha A. V., Tsvyntarna I. Ya.</i> LEVELS PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN THE THIRD-YEAR STUDENTS OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITY.	119
17.	<i>Yakymenko D. O., Smiianov Ye. V., Plakhtiienko I. O.</i> THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT FOR ADENOIDITIS IN THE ADULT POPULATION.	124
18.	<i>Yevstihnieiev I. V.</i> EXTRAPULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS: FOCUS ON IMPROVING DIAGNOSIS.	127
19.	<i>Аветісова І. С., Семак А. В.</i> ПРАКТИЧНЕ ВИКОРИСТАННЯ ТЕХНОЛОГІЧНИХ ІНОВАЦІЙ В СУЧАСНИХ МЕТОДИКАХ ДИСТАНЦІЙНОГО ВИКЛАДАННЯ ІНОЗЕМНИХ МОВ.	130
20.	<i>Авлакулов А. М.</i> ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГОРИЗОНТАЛЬНЫХ СКВАЖИН НА МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИИ ЮЖНЫЙ КЕМАЧИ.	138
21.	<i>Азизова Фарида Фахритдин Кзи</i> ВЛИЯНИЕ ПОВЫШЕННОГО ВНУТРИБРЮШНОГО ДАВЛЕНИЯ НА ГЕМОДИНАМИЧЕСКИЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ БОЛЬНЫХ С ВЕНТРАЛЬНЫМИ ГРЫЖАМИ.	143
22.	<i>Амонов А., Джураев А., Бехбудов Ш.</i> НОВАЯ УСТРОЙСТВА ДЛЯ НАНЕСЕНИЯ ПОЛИМЕРНОЙ КОМПОЗИЦИИ НА СТАЧИВАЕМЫЕ ДЕТАЛИ ОДЕЖДЫ.	148
23.	<i>Аскарьянц В. П., Ларин Е. А., Субханкулов Ж. Г., Атоев Ж. А.</i> АСПЕКТЫ ФИЗИОЛОГИИ ДЫХАНИЯ.	153
24.	<i>Байназарова О. О.</i> УПРАВЛІННЯ ЯКІСТЮ ЗАГАЛЬНОЇ СЕРЕДНЬОЇ ОСВІТИ В ОБ'ЄДНАНІЙ ТЕРИТОРІАЛЬНІЙ ГРОМАДІ: ТЕОРЕТИЧНІ ЗАСАДИ.	161
25.	<i>Белостоцкая Н. Н., Коляда И. И., Морская А. А.</i> ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИХ АЛГОРИТМОВ В ДИЗАЙНЕ.	169
26.	<i>Білецька І. О.</i> РОЛЬ ДИСКУРСИВНИХ ЧИННИКІВ У ПРОЦЕСІ ФОРМУВАННЯ ОЦІНОЧНИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК КОНЦЕПТУ MULTICULTURALISM І СПОСОБИ ЇХ МОВНОЇ РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦІЇ.	177
27.	<i>Брославська Г. М.</i> ВИЗНАЧАЛЬНІ ЕТАПИ ЕФЕКТИВНОГО ЗАСТОСУВАННЯ В ОСВІТІ ЦИФРОВИХ ІНСТРУМЕНТІВ.	186

UDC 621.313.322

**THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL DIRECTIONS FOR THE
TURBOGENERATORS CREATION, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE
ELECTRIC POWER INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT**

Shevchenko Valentina Vladimirovna

Ph.D., docent

Shayda Viktor Petrovich

Ph.D., docent

Pototsky Dmitry

Senior Lecturer

National Technical University "KhPI"

Kharkiv, Ukraine

Annotation: The paper identifies the main tasks of ensuring the country's energy independence in terms of contemporary problems associated with environmental problems, population growth, and an increase in its energy activity. It has been established that nuclear power plants will be the main sources of electricity for a long time, therefore, it is important to improve turbogenerators (TG). The directions were established in which research should be carried out in order to eliminate the lag behind world firms in the field of turbogenerator engineering: increasing the power in unit of execution, reducing the TG mass and dimensions, replacing hydrogen cooling with air cooling.

Key words: electric power industry, energy efficiency, environmental safety, forecasting the electric power industry development, turbogenerators, capacity increase.

Over the past 50 years, the world's population has almost doubled, the consumption of electricity has increased 4 times, the total technical and energy activity has grown 5 times, which requires a further increase in electricity generation.

The world population is increasing by about 80 million people a year. The need to increase the number and capacity of turbogenerators (TGs) is determined by scientific forecasting of the electric power industry development and is reflected in the "Energy Strategy of Ukraine for the Period until 2035", where it is indicated that the main task of ensuring the country's energy independence is to improve the technical and economic characteristics of thermal power plants and nuclear power plants, i.e., TG, Fig. 1, [1,2,11].

Fig. 1. The dynamics of population growth and world electricity consumption in 1950–2050.

Scientists from different countries were engaged in forecasting the development of technology and economics, but at present in world science these concepts are associated with the name of the famous economist N.D. Kondratyev (the "Kondratyev's long waves" theory or the cyclical development theory). This theory is the basis for predicting the most probable direction for the electric power industry development [3,7,13]. Development of industry, economy, social programs from the third "Kondratyev wave" depends on sufficient electricity generation, on the electric power systems reliability functioning and electrical equipment, that is, on the reliability of the TG [4,7,9]. The forecast was carried out for the stagnation and stabilization scenario of the electric power industry development, which, in our opinion, is the most possible and promising for Ukraine [6,11-13].

In Ukraine, the energy efficiency program is rather difficult to implement due to the following problems:

1) the lack of methods for selecting and evaluating the operation of energy-efficient equipment, the creation of modern programs for its service.

2) lack of funding mechanisms for the design, creation and implementation of new technology;

3) the lack of training programs that can quickly respond to the emergence of new equipment, who are able to quickly rebuild for its effective operation [8].

The frequency of the current (voltage) in the power grid of Ukraine in recent decades has been at the level of 49.5÷49.7 Hz due to changes in the magnitude and nature of the loads, large "dips" and "peaks" of energy consumption, due to a significant contribution to the power system of electricity from TPPs, the equipment of which worn out. Reducing the frequency of voltage in network further is dangerous: when the voltage frequency decreases to 49.0 Hz, the reactors of NPP power units must be unloaded to 10% of the rated power [5,6]. This can lead to an additional avalanche-like increase in the power deficit in the power system and create an emergency [8,12]. There is also the problem of regulating the magnitude of the voltage in the power system. In order for the voltage to be rated, it is necessary to adjust the reactive power balance. Seasonal, daily and other "dips" or "peaks" of electricity consumption, load changes in 220÷750 kV lines lead to the appearance of significant reactive power and to an increase in voltage [7,11].

The most effective method for regulating the voltage in the network is to change the operating modes of powerful generators of TPPs and NPPs: changing the ratio of generated active and reactive energy, including a complete transition to the compensator mode; transfer of the TG to work with increased values of the power factor ($\cos\varphi$), for example, up to 0.995. In this case, the reactive power, which is given to the network, decreases. This mode will not affect the overall stability of the generators, because the main condition for ensuring static stability is the correct choice of setting the feedback coefficients of the field current regulators in the electromagnetic torque control circuit. But this leads to cyclic electrodynamic and

thermomechanical effects on the TG, to their accelerated degradation, to a decrease in the availability and utilization factor of power units [8,13]. World practice provides for the modernization of electrical equipment of power plants every 8-10 years, but in Ukraine such an update has not been carried out since the 80s-90s of the 20-th century. The global energy crisis, which determines the state of the economy in our country, the political state of Ukraine does not allow for the planned modernization of the power plants' EO. Only partial modernization is economically possible.

The modernization programs should ensure the improvement of the TG technical and economic characteristics:

- expanding the operating range and increasing reliability by improving the quality of manufacture, installation, maintenance and repair work at power plant units;

- when creating a TG, it is necessary to use new technologies, active and insulating materials, design solutions, modern cooling systems;

- increase in the power of the TG due to an increase in electromagnetic loads while ensuring static and dynamic stability, permissible thermal conditions.

The task of creating domestic TGs is to increase their energy efficiency and ensure competitiveness in the world market [5,7].

It should be noted that the selected solutions must be economically feasible and correspond to the technological capabilities of not only electrical machine building, but also related industries:

- 1) the capabilities of metallurgical enterprises. In Ukraine, it is possible to manufacture rotors weighing 110-120 tons (weight of the casting-billet 270 tons, plant "Azovstal", Mariupol). It can be concluded that in Ukraine it is currently possible to manufacture TG-s with a capacity of no more than 1000-1200 MW. In world practice, castings weighing more than 300 tons will not be cast in the near future either. A further increase in the power of the TG is possible only by increasing the electromagnetic loads and voltage (up to 27 kV) to maintain the rotors mass and size parameters;

- 2) the problem of transporting TG to the consumer. When transporting by rail,

the permissible mass of goods is determined by the Rules of the Road: the maximum carrying capacity of railroad transporters of the connected type is 500 tons; transportation of goods up to 24 m long is possible (length of the rotor of a 1000 MW TG with an exciter); the outer diameter of the TG body should not exceed 6.4-6.5 m, otherwise it will be necessary to expand bridges and tunnels, to stop the oncoming traffic of trains.

There are also restrictions on the active length of the rotor: turbine steels make it possible to manufacture rotors with a length of no more than 8.5 m (distance between support bearings) and with an outer diameter of 1.90 m [7,11];

3) in world practice, they have reached the limit of increasing the power of turbines and reactors. For TGs of higher power, new types of turbines with increased throughput and new types of controlled nuclear reactors are required.

Over the past fifty years, the unit capacity of the TG has increased by 7-7.5 times, from 200 to 1500 MW, and work continues to increase it. Foreign companies, when creating new TGs with a large nominal power (over 11000÷1500 MW), are guided by a 4-pole version (companies *Mitsubishi Heavy Industries*», Japan, «*General Electric*» and «*Westinghouse Electric Company*» (USA); «*Kraftwerkunion*» (Germany); «*Brown Boveri*» (Switzerland). Currently, General Electric is working on the creation of two TGs with a capacity of 1,750 MW for nuclear power plants in China; in Great Britain and the USA they are designing TG a 2000 MW. The maximum capacity of TGs installed at French NPPs is 1550 MW [7].

After analyzing the state of the power equipment of Ukrainian stations, the tasks of improving domestic turbine generators were set taking into account global trends [7]. The directions were established in which the research of TGs should be carried out in order to avoid lagging behind world firms: increasing the power of TGs in a unit of execution, reducing the mass and dimensions of TGs with a simultaneous increase in power without changing the dimensions, replacing hydrogen cooling with air.

To confirm the prospects of increasing the TG unit power, we will show that the specific consumption of materials, mass and losses in one TG are less than in

several TGs of the same total power.

The specific consumption of materials with an increase in the power of the TG decreases, because the relationship between the power and the weight of the TG is nonlinear: for a TG with a capacity of 30 MW, the specific consumption of materials was 2.75 kg/kW, for a TG with a capacity of 800 MW it is equal to 0.58 kg/kW [6,7].

The specific material consumption of TG is equal to $K_G = G'/P_{sN}$, kg/kW,

where G' – mass of the designed TG: $G' = q_G \cdot D_{out}^2 \cdot l_s \cdot 10^{-6}$ кг;

q_G – equivalent "density" of TG, kg/m³

$$q_G = \frac{G}{V} = \frac{G}{\pi \cdot D_{out}^2 \cdot l_{out}},$$

G – mass of the base TG, kg; D_{out} – outer diameter of the TG body, m;

l_{out} – total length of the TG stator housing, m.

TG design power:

$$P_s \sim j \cdot q_{eff} \cdot w_s \cdot B_{mid} \cdot S_{mid} \cdot n_s;$$

where j – current density A/mm²; q_{eff} – cross-sectional area of the effective winding conductor, mm²; B_{mid} – the average value of the magnetic induction of the magnetic circuit considered section S_{mid} , Tл; w_s – the number of stator winding turns; n_s – frequency of the stator magnetic field rotation, rpm.

The total cross-sectional area of all winding turns $q_{eff} \cdot w_s = S_0$, mm².

We can write: $P_s \sim j \cdot B_{mid} \cdot n_s \cdot l_s^4$ and $S_{mid} \cdot S_0 \sim l_s^2 \cdot l_s^2 = l_s^4$.

For geometrically similar machines in which $j = \text{const}$ and $B_{mid} = \text{const}$, the following relations are fulfilled:

$$P_s/n_s \sim l_s^4 \quad \text{and} \quad l_s \sim \sqrt[4]{\frac{P_s}{n_s}} \sim \sqrt[4]{M_{elm}},$$

where TG electromagnetic moment $M_{elm} \sim P_s/n_s$.

The TG length l_s is proportional to $\sqrt[4]{P_s}$. For machines with similar designs, the ratio of the same dimensions (diameters D_s , lengths l_s , height h_{z1} and width of grooves $b_{gr.i}$) is equal:

$$D_{s1}/D_{s2} = l_{s1}/l_{s2} = h_{z1}/h_{z2} = b_{gr.1}/b_{gr.2}$$

The turbogenerator mass G is proportional to its volume, i.e., the linear

dimensions to the third power:

$$G \sim l_s^3 \sim \left(\sqrt[4]{P_s}\right)^3 = \sqrt[4]{P_s^3}$$

The amount losses in the machine (ΣP_i) at given values j and B proportional to machine weight and linear dimensions (l_s):

$$\Sigma P_i \sim l_s^3 \sim \sqrt[4]{P_s^3}.$$

Specific values of mass and losses related to the power of the TG:

$$G/P_s \sim \Sigma P_i/P_s \sim \sqrt[4]{P_s^3}/P_s = 1/\sqrt[4]{P_s}.$$

The ratio of the total mass G_m and total losses ΣP_m of several (m) identical machines to the mass G and losses P_i of one machine, the power of which is equal to the sum of the capacities of these m machines ($P_{s\Sigma} = m \cdot P_s$) can be written

$$\frac{G_m}{G} \approx \frac{\Sigma P_m}{P} \approx \frac{m \cdot \sqrt[4]{P_s^3}/m^3}{\sqrt[4]{P_s^3}} = \frac{m}{\sqrt[4]{m^3}} = \sqrt[4]{m}.$$

That is, the total mass and losses of several TG-s are always greater than the mass and losses of one TG with the same total power.

It should be noted that with an increase in the TG power, the stability of its operation on the network decreases, since the mass of the rotor increases disproportionately to the increase in power (less): in powerful TG-s, the rotors become relatively lighter (kg/kW), less inertial and less stable in emergency modes

Conclusions

1) it is necessary to use a systematic approach, take into account the cyclical nature of development, introduce new directions in solving problems of the electric power industry, when analyzing its state and establishing development directions.

2) The important technical and economic indicators of the reliability and efficiency of the energy system are the reliability and efficiency of large TGs, which must be competitive in the global energy market and ensure the generation of the required electricity. The perfection of the structures and parameters of the TG is decisive in the development of the electric power industry in any scenario in any country.

3) To improve the TG designs with an increase in power without changing the

dimensions and to ensure their competitiveness in the world energy market, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- introduce progressive technological processes into production, use modern steels and insulating materials, use new cooling systems (air cooling instead of hydrogen cooling);

- to develop measures to reduce the mass and dimensions of the TG with an increase in power, TG with an air-cooling system to ensure their competitiveness.

REFERENCES

1. Enerhetychna stratehiia Ukrainy na period do 2035 roku. – <https://mepr.gov.ua/news/34422.html>

2. World Energy Outlook 2019. France, Paris: International Energy Agency, 2019 (ISBN 978-92-64-52327-2). – 810 p.

3. Shevchenko V. V. Perspektivnaya ocenka sovershenstvovaniya e`nergeticheskoy sistemy` Ukrainy` // E`lektrika. – 2012. – №9. – С. 10-15.

4. Bushuev V. V., Mastepanov A. M. Krizisy` budushhego: perspektivy` mirovoj e`konomiki i e`nergetiki do 2050 goda // E`nergeticheskaya politika. – 2010. – № 4–5. – С. 13-19.

5. Minko A. N., Shevchenko V. V. Sovershenstvovanie teploobmenny`kh sistem turbogeneratorov s czel`yu povы`sheniya ikh e`ffektivnosti // Problemele energeticii regionale (ISSN 1857-0070; Moldova, Kishinev). – 2019. – № 1(39). – Pp. 80-89.

6. Shevchenko V. V. To issue of ensuring of competitiveness of domestic turbogenerators // Electrical and computer systems: special. release "Electrical and computer systems: theory and practice" (Odessa, 26-28 June 2016). – № 22(98). – Pp. 226-231

7. Shevchenko Valentina. Perspektivy` sozdaniya konkurentosposobny`kh turbogeneratorov TE`S i AE`S. – Germany: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing. – 2016. – 137 p.

8. Shevchenko V.V. The reform of the higher education of Ukraine in the

conditions of the military-political crisis. // International Journal of Educational Development. – 2018. – № 65. – Pp. 237-253.

9. Barilo V. V., Golodnova O. S. Osobennosti ocenki e`konomicheskoy e`ffektivnosti zatrat na modernizaciyu generiruyushhego oborudovaniya s chel`yu povy`sheniya ego nadezhnosti //E`lektrotehnika. E`lektroe`nergetika. E`lektrotekhnicheskaya promy`shlennost`. – 2006. – № 4. – С. 3-11.

10. Liese M., Boer J., Gern R. Life extension methods and experiences with turbine generator rehabilitation and upgrading. Siemens AG // CIGRE Session 2008. – Report 12-15. – Pp. 11-104.

11. Kentsiczkiy O.G. Razvitie nauchny`kh osnov i razrabotka sredstv povy`sheniya pokazatelej bezotkaznosti moshhny`kh turbo-i gidrogeneratorov // Enerhetychna stratehiia Ukrainy na period do 2035 roku. Pratsi Instytutu elektrodynamiky NANU. – 2019. – Vyp. 53. – С. 39-47.

12. Katayama H, Kakiuchi M, et al. Development and production of the world's largest capacity 2p – 671MVA and 4p – 370 MVA hydrogen-cooled TG-s for a 60Hz – 900MW cross-compound thermal power plant // Rapport A1-102, CIGRE-2010

13. Shevchenko V. V. Razvitie sistem okhlazhdeniya turbogeneratorov i teoriya dlinny`kh voln Kondrat`eva // E`lektrika. – 2014. – № 8. – С. 12-14.

In English cite as:[Shevchenko VV, Shayda VP, Pototsky DV. Theoretical and practical directions for the turbogenerators creation, taking into account the electric power industry development. Proceedings of the 9th International scientific and practical conference "Fundamental and applied research in the modern world" (USA, Boston, 14-16 Apr 2021). USA: BoScience Publisher, 2021: 110-8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4818355>]

Keywords: turbogenerators, TG, energy independence, ecology, nuclear power plants, power increase, cooling, weight and dimensions.